

Studies in Some Ketoanil Complexes. Part III.

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Stoichiometry and stability of Zn(II) and Fe(III) complexes with three bidentate ketoanils as ligands have been determined in acetone spectrophotometrically. 1 : 1 Electrolytic nature of all the complexes has been established by molar conductance measurements. Magnetic measurements on the solid products have shown their para and diamagnetic nature, and octahedral and tetrahedral stereochemistry respectively. I.R. spectral studies of ligands and their complexes have revealed carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms as the coordination centres. Electronic spectra of Fe(III) complex has also been studied to investigate d-d electronic transitions and charge transfer.

IN continuation of our early communications¹⁻⁵, the present paper reports the studies in the composition, electrolytic and magnetic nature and structure of Zn(II) and Fe(III) complexes of bidentate ligands, *p*-iodo-(A), *p*-diethylamino-(B) and *p*-dimethylamino-(C) anils of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal. The structures of the ligands possessing donor abilities at carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms is shown below

(where R=phenanthrene nucleus and X=I, N(C₂H₅)₂ or N(CH₃)₂ for A, B and C respectively).

Experimental

Materials used : Both the metal chlorides and solvents used were B.D.H (L.R) products. However, all the three ligands were self synthesized and used after recrystallisation.

Apparatus, techniques and methods ; Stoichiometric studies of the complexes in acetone were made on spectronic '20' spectrophotometer by the method of Job⁶, Mole-Ratio⁷ and Slope-Ratio⁸. Optical density measurements were made at 520 nm (Zn-A), 420 nm (Zn-B), 585 nm (Zn-C) and 420 nm (Fe-C) of the complex on metal—ligand mixture solutions which were kept for a long time (overnight) in test tubes with air tight stoppers in order to ensure equilibrium or colour saturation. Conductometric measurements were made with Toshniwal's conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra of A and B ligands and their Zn(II) complexes were recorded in Nujol-mull on Beckmann 621-spectrophotometer while i.r. spectra of ligand C and its Fe(III) complex were recorded in KBr pellet on Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrophotometer. Gouy balance was used for magnetic measurements.

Preparations : Synthesis and characterisation of the ligands have already been reported⁹.

Ligand solutions were prepared by dissolving

accurately weighed quantity directly in acetone. Metal chloride solutions were standardised¹⁰ before use.

Complexes were isolated from the acetone solution containing appropriate amount of the reactants. The reaction mixture was concentrated by evaporation and the products were crystallised at room temperature. Dark complexes obtained were washed with ether to remove any unreacted ligand and purified by recrystallisation from acetonitrile. Products were dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Analysis : Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses of the complexes were performed at I.I.T., Kanpur. Chloride and metal were estimated gravimetrically¹⁰. The results of elemental analyses [Zn—A complex—Found% : C, 46.18 ; H, 2.35 ; N, 2.32 ; Cl, 12.36 ; Zn, 11.80. Zn(C₂₂H₁₄NO)Cl₂ requires % : C, 46.22 ; H, 2.45 ; N, 2.45 ; Cl, 12.41 ; Zn, 11.44. Zn—B complex—Found % : C, 60.20 ; H, 4.52 ; N, 5.28 ; Cl, 13.67 ; Zn, 13.00. Zn(C₂₆H₂₄N₂O)Cl₂ requires % : C, 60.44 ; H, 4.65 ; N, 5.42 ; Cl, 13.73 ; Zn, 12.66. Zn—C complex—Found % : C, 58.47 ; H, 3.99 ; N, 5.90 ; Cl, 14.08 ; Zn, 13.62. Zn(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)Cl₂ requires % : C, 58.98 ; H, 4.09 ; N, 5.73 ; Cl, 14.51 ; Zn, 13.38. Fe—C complex—Found % : C, 66.38 ; H, 4.70 ; N, 6.00 ; Cl, 12.20 ; Fe, 6.92. Fe(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)Cl₂ requires % : C, 66.49 ; H, 4.62 ; N, 6.46 ; Cl, 12.28 ; Fe, 6.45] give 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 stoichiometry for the solid Zn(II) and Fe(III) complexes respectively, as arrived in solution.

Results and Discussion

Spectrophotometric studies : The λ_{max} for the ligands A, B and C and their zinc(II) and iron(III) complexes were determined as 550 nm (A), 360 nm (B), 400 nm (C), 520 nm (Zn-A), 420 nm (Zn-B), 585 nm (Zn-C) and 420 nm (Fe-C) following the method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹¹. These results indicate the formation of only one complex species in each case during the interaction of the reactants.

The Job's method of equimolar ($0.40 \times 10^{-3} M$) solutions at constant total volume of 10ml. also gave the same molar composition for the zinc (II) and iron(III) complexes. Absorption curves showed maxima around 0.50 for the Zn(II) systems and at 0.33 for the Fe(III) system. In the mole-ratio method, equimolar ($0.25 \times 10^{-3} M$) solutions of the reactants were used. Inflexions on the absorption curves indicated the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes for zinc(II) and iron(III) systems respectively. Slope-ratio method also gave the same stoichiometries of the complexes. Stability constants (Ks) of the complexes were calculated using mole-ratio method and values obtained were as 4.89×10^6 , 30.62×10^6 , 39.90×10^6 and 6.55×10^{12} respectively at room temperature (305°K).

Solid state studies : The magnetic moments of the solid products determined at 295°K. were 0.50, 0.54, 0.66 and 5.80 BM zn(II)- and Fe(III) complexes respectively.

Molar conductance (ΛM) values of 15.25, 13.78, 13.28 and 12.69 Mhos of Zn(II) and Fe(III) complexes in nitrobenzene respectively suggesting^{1,2} 1 : 1 electrolytic nature.

Comparison and perusal of i.r. spectra of the ligands and their complexes indicated that most of the frequencies are perturbed on complex formation. Strong peaks in the region 1653-1667 cm^{-1} and 1600-1613 cm^{-1} corresponding to $>C=O$ and $>C=N$ groups of ligands respectively are shifted to lower values 1645-1650 cm^{-1} and 1540-1600 cm^{-1} on complex formation, showing participation of these groups in complexation. Appearance of new bands at 296-300 cm^{-1} and at 390-478 cm^{-1} for Zn(II) complexes, attributable¹³⁻¹⁵ to metal-oxygen and metal-nitrogen bonds respectively support the above conclusion. The shift in the frequency of $C=C$ aromatic (1493-1575 cm^{-1}) to lower values (1480-1504 cm^{-1}) gives evidence for conjugation¹⁶ in the ligands during complexation. If the bond at 813-820 cm^{-1} in the ligands is considered to be due to para substitution, then its shift to lower value (800-813 cm^{-1}) in the complexes indicates the possibility of change of the benzenoid structure of the ligand to a quinonoid structure in the course of complexation.

In the electronic spectrum of Fe(III) system under study three bands around 18182 cm^{-1} (ϵ , 200), 19802 cm^{-1} (ϵ , 320) and 25316 cm^{-1} (ϵ , 1900) were observed in the visible region. The early two bands with very low extinction in comparison to third and last band may only be assigned¹⁷⁻¹⁹ to spin-forbidden transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (G) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (G) respectively. However, third band (doublet) with very high ϵ value may be attributed¹⁹ to the charge transfer from the ligand to the metal. Some of the ligand field parameters, viz. $10D_q$, B and β have also been calculated¹⁹ and their values are 8323 cm^{-1} , 757.6 cm^{-1} and 0.58 respectively.

Octahedral stereochemistry is suggested to the chelate involving spin-free d^5 configuration of Fe(III) This is supported by the magnetic moment (μ_B) value reported earlier. It has also been revealed that *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal is a strong field ligand. Citing great many examples²⁰, tetrahedral stereochemistry involving sp^3 hybridisation may be suggested for Zn(II) diamagnetic complexes with d^{10} configuration.

From the above results tentatively the following formulae and general structure may be suggested which satisfy maximum coordination number of four for Zn(II) and six for Fe(III) complexes

where $L=A, B$ or C and $M=\text{metal ion}$.

The stability constants of the Zn(II) complexes are in order $A < B < C$ of ligands. This sequence is in the order of electron donating tendency of substituents on the phenyl ring.

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